

Quality Assurance in Secondary Education for Sustainable Development in Rivers and Bayelsa State, Nigeria

Kalagbor Gbeke, I. (Ph.D), Amadi Kenneth (Ph.D) & Nnadiyeze G. C.

Department of Educational Management,
Faculty of Education,
Rivers State University, Port Harcourt, Rivers State

Corresponding Authors' Email: ibienegbeke@gmail.com; godfrey.nnadiyeze@ust.edu.ng;
kristamadi2016@gmail.com

Abstract

This study examined quality assurance in secondary education for sustainable development in Rivers and Bayelsa States, Nigeria. The study which adopted descriptive survey design was guided by two research questions and two hypotheses. The population of the study comprised 365 public senior secondary school principals in Rivers and Bayelsa States. A sample of 146 principals (80 male and 66 female) was drawn through stratified random sampling technique. A questionnaire titled: "Quality Assurance in Secondary Education for Sustainable Development Questionnaire (QASESDQ)" developed by the researcher was used for data collection. The instrument which had 18 items was properly validated and the test of reliability yielded 0.81 using Cronbach Alpha Method. Mean standard deviation and rank order were used to analyze the research questions, while z-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The results of the study revealed among others that the challenges of quality assurance in secondary education for sustainable development in Rivers and Bayelsa States are inadequate infrastructure/facilities; poor funding; inadequate motivation/poor conditions of service; inadequate supervision. The study also revealed that factors that can enhance quality assurance include among others employment of qualified teachers; employment of adequate number of teachers; adequate provision of infrastructure/facilities; and adequate motivation of teachers. Based on these findings, conclusion was drawn and the following recommendations among others were made: secondary school principals and supervisors from Ministry of Education should intensify their efforts in instructional and schools' supervision to enhance quality assurance in secondary education.

Keywords: Secondary Education, Quality, Quality Assurance, Sustainable Development

INTRODUCTION

Secondary education is one of the major levels of education in Nigeria. It is the education that children receive after primary education and before entering into tertiary institution (FRN, 2014). It is a very important level of education that is saddled with the responsibility of preparing students for two major things; useful living within the society and for higher education. Preparing students for useful living within the society embraces a lot of things such as character development, language and communication skills development, cognitive/creative reasoning, technical/vocational skills development; and manpower training at sub-professional levels. Secondary education plays a vital role in the pursuit of sustainable development in Nigeria and the Niger Delta region in particular. Without sound and qualitative secondary education, it will be difficult to achieve sustainable development anywhere in Nigeria.

It is therefore very imperative to guarantee the quality of academic activities and other co-curricular programmes going on at this level of education. Quality could be seen as the level of value in a product. According to Akpan (2011), it is something considered good or worthy in preference to others, or simply the degree of excellence of a service or activity. Quality may be considered as the basis of how good and effective the teachers are, how adequate and accessible the facilities and materials needed for effective teaching and learning are, and how well prepared secondary school graduates are to meet the challenges of life and for solving the problems of the society (Bassey & Bassey, 2008).

Quality assurance is the process of ensuring that the learners are maximally equipped with the relevant knowledge, skills and attitude as they are stated in the national policy on education. Secondary school principals who are at the fore front of quality assurance need to adopt mechanisms that will ensure adequate provision and utilization of resources to enhance the achievement of educational goals and sustainable development. They motivate behaviours and attitudes in the school as the image makers and role models who influence teachers and students greatly (Okorji,

Igbokwe & Ezeugbor, 2016). Okeke-James, Igbokwe, Anyanwu and Ogbo (2020) suggested that following as ways principals can influence quality assurance for sustainable development: adequate planning, adequate room for improvisation, in-service training, in-school supervision, periodic appraisal, and principals' annual evaluation.

Other factors that create room for quality assurance is the recruitment of qualified teachers. Teaching according to Emenalo (2009) is a profession and professionalism in education implies a commitment to the needs of students and an obligation to meet their needs by adopting the most appropriate pedagogic practices. Adequate funding also contributes to quality assurance because funding is the life wire of every viable organization. Modern secondary education requires a lot of money and huge amount of resources for effective functioning. It costs so much to provide adequate laboratories, libraries, workshops, classrooms, instructional materials, recreational facilities etc needed by the staff and the students for effective teaching and learning. Facilities and equipment required in secondary education should be adequately provided to enhance access and effective utilization that will promote quality assurance and sustainable development (Bassey, 2002). There is also the need for commitment to handwork. Both the teachers and the students must be adequately committed to hard work and scholarship rather than indulging in cultism, truancy, examination malpractice etc.

Quality assurance in secondary education is challenged by a lot of factors which include:

1. Inadequate school plant/facilities
2. Poor funding of secondary education in Nigeria
3. Poor conditions for service of teachers in Nigeria
4. Poor supervision practices (internal and external)
5. Inadequacy of teachers (in quality and quantity)
6. Poor commitment of teachers and students to hard work
7. Poor quality of students
8. Employee's resistance to change and innovations

The school plant comprises of all the infrastructures and facilities required for conducive learning environment and effective teaching and learning. They include school buildings, classrooms, offices, libraries, recreational facilities, laboratories etc. Quality assurance should begin with the quality planning and provision of infrastructures and school facilities. The quality and the level of provision of school infrastructure and facilities in secondary schools in Nigeria is inadequate. Most secondary schools in Nigeria especially those located in rural areas lack conducive classrooms, teachers staff room, libraries, laboratories and other contemporary facilities such as computers and ICT studio or laboratory. Akomolafe in Agabi (2014) observed that teaching and learning in the contemporary society require adequate provision of quality school abilities for quality education delivery. ICT is not only a tool to make teaching/learning in the classroom vivid and real, but it reshapes education in terms of technology and pedagogical innovations (Agabi, 2014). ICT facilities in public secondary schools in Nigeria are grossly inadequate.

Poor funding of secondary education in Nigeria have remained a serious challenge to quality assurance. This is promoted by planning of education with inaccurate data, inaccurate enrolment projections and poor commitment to funding of education by the political class. According to Okoro and Iyeke (2004), availability of requisite facilities is important for the effective execution of any assigned task. Funding affects the provision of facilities and recruitment of teachers necessary for quality assurance in the education sector. Where these facilities and staff personnel are inadequately provided, quality assurance may be seriously hindered. Motivation is a very important factor in service delivery and productivity. Motivation is a combination of all the forces characterizing an innate state which activates and directs overt behaviour towards goal achievement (Ukeje, Okorie & Nwagbara, 1992). A teacher can strive for effectiveness by the adoption and application of appropriate teaching methodology if he is adequately motivated, otherwise the teacher may become indifferent to the result of his teaching. The poor motivation of teachers and poor conditions of service teachers are exposed to in Nigeria undermines quality assurance.

School supervision is a major administrative task function of the school principal. It is aimed at guiding the teachers in the achievement of instructional effectiveness and attainment of stated curricular objectives (Akinwumiji & Agabi, 2013). Both internal and external supervision are poorly carried out due to poor motivation, corruption and inadequate provision of facilities. Compromising adequate supervision implies that quality assurance is compromised. Teachers occupy an important position in quality assurance. The quality and quantity of teachers in secondary education service delivery are very necessary in quality assurance of secondary education in Nigeria. While you have enough teachers in school located in urban areas, the reverse is the case with schools in rural areas.

Many people in the teaching field are not professionally trained, as such lack the professional competence required for effective teaching. The teacher/student ratio is also high which implies that, there is so much work for secondary school teachers in Nigeria. These factors have adverse effect on quality assurance.

Related to the above factors is the poor commitment to teachers and students to hardwork. Due to lack of motivation, poor conditions of service and poor supervision practices, most secondary school teachers in Nigeria are poorly commitment to their duties. They are irregular to school; perambulate from one corner to another whenever they come around. The students are busy with their phones and do not have time for their studies any longer. They prefer ways or short cuts to pass their exams; hence they indulge in examination malpractice. This is a total disregard for quality assurance in secondary education system in Nigeria. Poor commitment of teachers and students to hardwork has resulted to poor quality students.

The resistance to change and innovation is another factor hindering quality assurance. Different people react differently to change. Strong resistance to change is associated with historical feelings and ways of doing things (Oredein, 2009). People resist change and innovations due to fear of the unknown, personal attitude, financial reasons, level of training and environment, habit as well as psychological reasons (Alimba, 2009). The increasing manifestation of resistance to change is a major hindrance to quality assurance.

Statement of the Problem

In Nigeria and Niger Delta region in particular, many people are of the believe that the standard of secondary education has fallen drastically. This believe is buttressed by the poor performance of secondary school students in both internal and external examinations, in most situation, such students poor performance are often blamed on the quality of teachers, quality of facilities and inadequate funding and poor supervision, lack of regard to the views and feelings of others, lack of regard for dignity of labour, and lack of regard for the norms and values binding the people together. This situation has led a lot of people to express their disappointment with secondary school graduates in terms of character development and learning. This situation has a negative impact on sustainable development. The situation is very disheartening; the researcher is bothered by this, hence, the motivation to examine quality assurance in secondary education for sustainable development in Rivers and Bayelsa States.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

This aim of this study was to examine quality assurance in secondary education for sustainable development in Rivers and Bayelsa States. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Ascertain the challenges of quality assurance in secondary education for sustainable development in Rivers and Bayelsa States.
2. Determine the factors that can enhance quality assurance in secondary education for sustainable development in Rivers and Bayelsa States.

Research Questions

The following research questions were answered in this study:

1. What are the challenges of quality assurance in secondary education for sustainable development in Rivers and Bayelsa States?
2. What are the factors that can enhance quality assurance in secondary education for sustainable development in Rivers and Bayelsa States?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

- Ho₁: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female principals on the challenges of quality assurance in secondary education for sustainable development in Rivers and Bayelsa States.
- Ho₂: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female principals on the factors that can enhance quality assurance in secondary education for sustainable development in Rivers and Bayelsa States.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted descriptive survey design. The population of the study comprised of three hundred and sixty-five (365) public senior secondary school principals (203 male and 162 female) in Rivers and Bayelsa States of Nigeria. (Source: Secondary Education Management Boards in Rivers and Bayelsa States, 2021 Report). A sample size of one hundred and forty-six (146) principals made up of eighty (80) male and sixty-six (66) female was drawn through stratified random sampling technique. This sample size represented 40% of the population of the study. Data was collected with a questionnaire entitled: “Quality Assurance in Secondary Education for Sustainable Development Questionnaire (QASESDQ)” developed by the researcher. The instrument contained 18 items that were structured using four-point rating Likert Scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD). The instrument was validated and the test of reliability through Cronbach Alpha method yielded an r-index of 0.83. A total of 146 copies of the questionnaire were distributed and retrieved. Mean, standard deviation, and rank order were used to analyze the research questions, while z-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULT

Research Question 1: What are the challenges of quality assurance in secondary education for sustainable development in Rivers and Bayelsa States?

Table 1: Mean scores, standard deviation and rank order analysis of the responses of male and female principals on the challenges of quality assurance in secondary education for sustainable development in Rivers and Bayelsa States

S/N	Challenges of quality assurance in secondary education for sustainable development	Male Principals N = 80						Female Principals N = 66						Means Set	Rank Order	Decision
		SA	A	D	SD	\bar{x}_1	STD	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{x}_2	STD			
1.	Inadequate quality/quantity of teachers.	34	27	8	11	3.05	0.64	26	20	11	9	2.95	0.69	3.00	3 rd	Agreed
2.	Inadequate infrastructure/facilities.	28	34	10	8	3.02	0.66	24	22	15	5	2.98	0.67	3.00	3 rd	Agreed
3.	Poor funding of secondary education	32	25	13	10	2.99	0.68	25	19	13	9	2.91	0.72	2.95	5 th	Agreed
4.	Inadequate motivation/poor conditions of service of teachers.	38	24	10	8	3.15	0.63	28	20	10	8	3.03	0.65	2.09	1 st	Agreed
5.	Inadequate internal/external supervision.	31	28	13	8	3.03	0.65	25	24	9	8	3.00	0.66	3.02	2 nd	Agreed
6.	Poor commitment of teachers/students to hardwork.	29	32	8	11	2.98	0.69	25	20	9	12	2.88	0.73	2.93	6 th	Agreed
7.	High attrition rate of teachers.	27	26	16	11	2.69	0.72	24	19	10	13	2.82	0.74	2.84	8 th	Agreed
8.	Poor quality of students.	14	19	24	23	2.30	0.75	16	15	16	19	2.42	0.76	2.36	9 th	Agreed
9.	Inadequate provision of capacity building/professional development programme.	24	27	13	16	2.74	0.73	24	23	11	8	2.95	0.71	2.85	7 th	Agreed
	Aggregate mean and standard deviation					2.90	0.68					2.88	0.70			

Criterion mean = 2.50

Data in table 1 shows that all the items had weighted mean set scores that are greater than the criterion mean (2.50) except item number 8. Item number 1 to 7 and 9 were accepted by the respondents as the challenges of quality assurance in secondary education for sustainable development in Rivers and Bayelsa States. In term of rank order, item number 4 and 5 rank 1st and 2nd respectively, while item 8 ranked 9th. Item 8 was rejected by the respondent as a challenge of quality assurance in secondary education for sustainable development in Rivers and Bayelsa States. The aggregate mean of 2.90 and 2.88 for male and female principals respectively indicated that the respondents unanimously agreed on the challenges of quality assurance in secondary education for sustainable development in Rivers and Bayelsa States.

Therefore, the challenges of quality assurance in secondary education for sustainable development in Rivers and Bayelsa States include the following: inadequate quality/ quantity of teachers; inadequate infrastructure/ facilities; poor funding of secondary education; inadequate motivation/ poor condition of service, inadequate internal/ external supervisor; poor commitment of teachers/ students to hard work; high attrition rate of teachers; and inadequate provision of capacity building/ professional development programmes.

Research Question 2: What are the factors that can enhance quality assurance in secondary education for sustainable development in Rivers and Bayelsa States?

Table 2: Mean scores, standard deviation and rank order analysis of the responses of male and female principals on the factor that can enhance quality assurance in secondary education for sustainable development in Rivers and Bayelsa States

S/N	Factors influencing quality assurance in secondary education for sustainable development	Male Principals N = 80						Female Principals N = 66						Means Set	Rank Order	Decision
		SA	A	D	SD	\bar{x}_1	STD	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{x}_2	STD			
1.	Employment of qualified teachers.	30	27	13	10	2.96	.65	26	21	15	4	3.05	.61	3.01	3 rd	Agreed
2.	Employment of adequate number of teachers.	26	35	11	8	2.99	.63	20	21	12	13	2.73	.68	2.86	7 th	Agreed
3.	Provision of adequate infrastructure.	34	27	11	8	3.09	.59	24	21	13	8	2.89	.66	2.98	3 rd	Agreed
4.	Adequate funding of secondary education.	29	35	8	8	3.06	.60	21	25	12	8	2.89	.66	2.98	6 th	Agreed
5.	Adequate supervision.	30	24	15	11	2.91	.67	23	20	7	16	2.76	.67	2.84	8 th	Agreed
6.	Organization of capacity/professional development programmes.	32	26	12	10	3.00	.61	26	20	12	8	2.97	.63	2.99	5 th	Agreed
7.	Adequate provision of instructional materials.	27	30	8	15	2.86	.68	28	22	10	06	3.24	.58	3.05	2 nd	Agreed
8.	Adequate motivation/conditions service for teachers.	40	29	8	3	3.33	.56	30	23	6	7	3.15	.57	3.24	1 st	Agreed
9.	Frequent review of the school curriculum.	16	13	26	25	2.25	.70	16	11	17	22	2.32	.71	2.29	9 th	Agreed
	Aggregate mean and standard deviation					2.94	.63					2.89	.64			

Criterion mean = 2.50

Data in table 2 show that all the items had weighted mean set scores that are greater than the criterion mean of 2.50 except item number 9. Items numbers 1 to 8 were accepted by the respondents as the factors that can enhance quality assurance in secondary education for sustainable development in Rivers and Bayelsa States. In term of rank order, item number 8 and 7 ranked 1st and 2nd respectively while item number 9 ranked 9th. Item 9 was rejected by the respondents as a factor that can enhance quality assurance in secondary education for sustainable development in Rivers and Bayelsa States. The aggregate weighted mean scores of 2.94 and 2.89 for male and female principals respectively showed that the respondents shared similar views on factor influencing quality assurance in secondary education for sustainable development.

Therefore, the factors that can enhance quality assurance in secondary education for sustainable development in Rivers and Bayelsa States include: employment of qualified teachers; employment of adequate number of teachers; provision of adequate infrastructure; adequate funding; adequate supervision; organization of capacity/professional development programmes; adequate provision of instructional materials; and adequate motivation/conditions of service for teachers.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female principals on the challenges of quality assurance in secondary education for sustainable development in Rivers and Bayelsa States.

Table 3: z-Test of Difference between the Mean Scores of Male and Female Principals on the Challenges of Quality Assurance in Secondary Education for Sustainable Development in Rivers and Bayelsa States.

Respondents	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	z-cal.	z-crit.	Level of sign.	Decision
Male principals	80	2.90	.68	144	0.174	± 1.960	0.05	Ho ₁
Female principals	66	2.88	.70					Not significant

Results in table 3 shows that the mean scores of male and female principals stood at 2.90 and 2.88 respectively. These mean scores look closely related. Furthermore, at 144 degrees of freedom and 0.05 level of significance, the calculated z-score of 0.174 was by far less than the z-critical value of ± 1.960 . The researcher therefore failed to reject the null hypothesis. This implies that, there is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female principals on the challenges of quality assurance in secondary education for sustainable development in Rivers and Bayelsa States.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female principals on the factors that can enhance quality assurance in secondary education for sustainable development in Rivers and Bayelsa States.

Table 4: z-test of difference between the Mean Scores of Male and Female Principals on the Factors that can Enhance Quality Assurance in Secondary Education for Sustainable Development in Rivers and Bayelsa States.

Respondents	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	z-cal.	z-crit.	Level of sign.	Decision
Male principals	80	2.94	.63	144	0.474	± 1.960	0.05	Ho ₂
Female principals	66	2.89	.64					Not significant

Results in table 4 indicate that the mean scores of male and female principals stood at 2.94 and 2.89 respectively. These mean scores appear to be closely related. Furthermore, at 144 degrees of freedom and 0.05 level of significance, the calculated z-score of 0.473 was by far less than the z-critical or table value of ± 1.960 . The researcher therefore, retained the null hypothesis. This implies that, there is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female principals on the factor that can enhance quality assurance in secondary education for sustainable development in Rivers and Bayelsa States.

Discussion of Findings

The study has revealed that the challenges of quality assurance in secondary education for sustainable development in Rivers and Bayelsa States include: inadequate quality/quantity of teachers; inadequate infrastructure facilities; poor funding; inadequate motivation; poor supervision; poor commitment; high attrition rate; and inadequate capacity building programme. Teachers are not evenly distributed in public secondary schools in Rivers and Bayelsa States. While some schools in urban areas have enough teachers, most schools in rural areas in these states grossly lack teachers in almost every subject area. This is a serious challenge to quality assurance. Moreover, some of these teachers are not professionally trained to teach. They lack the pedagogical skills and competencies to deliver quality teaching service. This finding is supported by Ayeni (2012) who stated that adequate recruitment of teachers in terms of quality and quantity is vital in effective management of secondary education in Nigeria.

Quality education begins with quality infrastructure and facilities required for effective teaching and learning. Unfortunately, most schools in some urban and rural areas in Rivers and Bayelsa States lack basic infrastructures/facilities that can support quality assurance or quality secondary education. These schools lack adequate libraries, laboratories, classrooms, recreational facilities, computers and ICT facilities, power supply etc. This finding is supported by Agabi (2014). Without these facilities quality assurance will be a mirage.

The poor motivation of teachers and poor conditions of service they are exposed to affects their morale and commitment to their duty. Teachers are poorly paid, salaries and allowances are seldomly paid on time and promotions are often withheld or granted without financial benefits. These affect their emotions, their families, their status in the society and their job due to lack of job satisfaction. This situation relegates quality assurance to the background due to their poor commitment to their duty.

Poor funding of education in Rivers and Bayelsa states have adversely affected quality assurance of secondary education, poor funding has adversely affected procurement and maintenance of school facilities, adequate employment of teachers, adequate supervision and provision of capacity development programmes. Poor funding is compounded by lack of political office holders to do the right thing and corruption which has eaten deep in every sector of our educational system. This finding supports by Okporo and Iyeke (2004).

School programmes are no longer supervised adequately by school principals and school's supervision team from the Ministry of Education. These officers compromise instructional effectiveness and attainment of stated curricular objectives due to their indifferent and non-challant attitude to their work. This finding is supported by Akinwuniyi and Agabi (2013) who observed that both internal and external supervision are poorly carried out due to lack of motivation and adequate facilities. This has a negative impact on quality assurance.

The study equally revealed that the factors that can enhance quality assurance in secondary education for sustainable development in Rivers and Bayelsa States include: employment of qualified teachers; adequate provision of infrastructure; adequate funding; adequate supervision; adequate motivation; adequate provision of instructional facilities; and adequate provision of capacity development programmes. To enhance quality assurance in secondary education in Rivers and Bayelsa States, government should employ well trained professional teachers in adequate number to bring down the teacher/student ratio to at least 1:40. This view is supported by FRN (2014). Most public secondary schools in Rivers and Bayelsa states lack enough teachers and some of teachers employed in these states are not qualified due to politicization of the appointment of teachers in these states.

Quality education is cost intensive. There is the need for adequate provision of infrastructure such as buildings for classrooms, laboratories, library, hostels etc. there is also the need for regular electricity supply and portable drinking water supply. Inadequate supply of these facilities make learning environment uncondusive and undermines quality assurance. Instructional materials are necessary for effective teaching/learning. It is unfortunate that they are inadequately provided for quality assurance in our secondary education supporting this observation Bassey (2002) stated that facilities and equipment required in secondary education should be adequately provided to enhance access, effective utilization and quality education.

Funding has been a major challenge for the provision of quality education. This has also been compounded by corruption among public officers in Rivers and Bayelsa states who embezzle public funds. Government needs to improve on their budgetary allocation to the education sector and display sincerity in the fight against corruption.

Quality assurance is part of the major responsibilities of the principal and the supervision department of the Ministry of Education. The principal and his team carry out internal supervision to check how teaching/learning are carried out. These efforts are complimented by the supervisory team from the Ministry of Education. It is unfortunate that both the internal and external supervision to promote quality assurance in secondary schools are compromised by those incharge. Government should motivate these people and the teachers adequately to enhance proper execution of their jobs in other to promote quality assurance.

Provision of adequate professional development programmes for knowledge and skills update by teachers is very necessary and will enhance quality assurance in secondary schools in Rivers and Bayelsa States. Teachers need professional development in their subject areas, ICT, classroom management, improvisation and utilization of instructional materials, modern pedagogical methods, assessment methods etc. Government hardly pay attention to this very important aspect of teachers' competency improvement which affects quality assurance in secondary education, improving teachers' competency skills through professional development programmes will enhance quality assurance in secondary education delivery in Rivers and Bayelsa States.

CONCLUSION

There are poor quality assurance practices in public secondary schools in Rivers and Bayelsa States due to inadequate: infrastructure, facilities, teachers, and teachers' motivation. Quality assurance in secondary education for sustainable development cannot be guaranteed in these states without paying adequate attention to these factors. Lack of adequate quality assurance in secondary education will have adverse effect on human capital development and the attainment of secondary education goals. It is therefore very important that government should address various factors affecting quality assurance in secondary education in these states without further delay.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Government should improve the conditions of service of teachers in public secondary schools in order to enhance their commitment to their duty.
2. Government should ensure that adequate infrastructure and instructional facilities are provided in public secondary schools in Rivers and Bayelsa States.
3. Secondary school principals and supervisors in Ministry of Education should intensify their efforts in instructional and schools' supervision to enhance quality assurance in secondary education.

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